

Galactic Center Newsletter

IAUS405: Traversing the Galactic Center in Space and Time, Brno (<https://gc2026.muni.cz/>)

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TRAVERSING THE GALACTIC CENTER

IN SPACE AND TIME

BRNO

CZECH REPUBLIC

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Symposium 405

Brno
Observatory
and Planetarium

MUNI

FROM THE EDITOR'S DESK

By VÁCLAV PAVLÍK

Dear friends and colleagues! Welcome to Brno, Czech Republic, and to the IAU Symposium 405: “Traversing the Galactic Center in Space and Time”. This gathering extends a lineage of “Galactic Center” workshops going back to the early 1980s (more on their history in the following article by Michal Zajaček), and for the first time, this Workshop is hosted in Brno, the capital of Moravia. To the general public, the Moravian region is widely known for its high-quality and award-winning wines. To those interested in science, let me recall that Brno was the

birthplace of Ernst Mach and Kurt Gödel, and the place where Gregor Johann Mendel laid the foundations of genetics.

The *Galactic Center Newsletter* – formerly published by the National Radio Astronomy Observatory between 1995 and 2008 – played a special role in connecting the Galactic Center research community. Long before today’s instant communication and online preprint culture, that was the platform where researchers shared updates, announced meetings, and highlighted new results. We are now bringing the *Newsletter* back – briefly for this Symposium, as Volume 29 – to continue its legacy, share scientific and cultural highlights, and capture the spirit of collaboration that has always defined our research.

It is a pleasure to have so many people drawn by the same gravitational pull of curiosity. Thanks to the joint effort by the SOC and LOC, we will explore the heart of our Galaxy as well as the heart of Moravia over the next five days. The scientific topics range from Sgr A*, through star formation and the dynamics of stellar populations of the central parsec, across the swirling gas of the Central Molecular Zone, and toward connections with other galactic nuclei. Despite decades of progress, many mysteries and unanswered questions remain. This meeting, therefore, aims to connect researchers from various fields to find the answers.

Let us join for scientific as well as informal discussions, and have a pleasant stay! ■

GALACTIC CENTER WORKSHOPS: FROM PASADENA TO BRNO

By MICHAL ZAJAČEK

The International Astronomical Union (IAU) Symposium 405, *Traversing the Galactic Center in Space and Time*, belongs to the now-traditional series of Galactic Center workshops (GCWs), which were initiated in the 1980s. Here, we provide a perspective on the evolution of GCWs in the context of the Galactic Center's multi-wavelength exploration.

The first GCW was organized in Pasadena, California, on January 7 and 8 in 1982. The total number of participants was about 92 [1]. The importance of the first GCW lies in the discussion of the nature of Sgr A*. At that time it had still been less than ten years since the identification of the compact radio source in Sagittarius [2], including its multi-wavelength variability. Actually, in 1982, the notation Sgr A* was introduced by Robert Brown to distinguish it from more extended and diffuse Sgr A. At the Pasadena workshop, participants discussed different scenarios to address the unusual properties of Sgr A*, such as, its high brightness temperature, small angular size, and variability. One of them was, naturally, an accreting black hole proposed a decade ago [3] but scenarios such as a protostar were also being discussed. At the first GCW a wealth of multi-wavelength data (radio, near-infrared and far-infrared, γ -ray) was presented to shed light on the multiphase circumnuclear medium.

In the following two decades, as the new ground-based as well as space-borne instruments were introduced, the description of the Galactic Center was built on more solid grounds. Especially in the 1990s, the application of speckle interferometry and the introduction of adaptive optics helped to reveal fast proper motions of S stars and their accelerations towards the end of the decade [4, 5]. The contributions presented at GCWs at this time converged towards the supermassive black hole paradigm with the mass of $\sim 2 - 4 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$ [6, 7, 8], with very little space for other alternatives. Notable meetings were held at Schloss Ringberg (Germany), La Serena (Chile), Kyoto (Japan), and Tucson (Arizona). The Galactic Center es-

tablished itself as the prototype of a normal, quiescent galactic nucleus.

In the 2000s, new capabilities emerged with space telescopes, such as Chandra and XMM-Newton, which allowed the discovery and coordinated X-ray-infrared-radio observations of Sgr A* flares. This helped constrain the dynamics of the Sgr A* accretion flow. Longer temporal baselines and more sensitive near-infrared imagers and spectroscopes significantly increased the number of well-constrained stellar orbits around Sgr A*. Notable GCWs include the 2002 workshop in Hawaii, USA [9], the 2006 edition in Bad Honnef, Germany [10], and the 2009 workshop in Shanghai, China [11].

The attention in the early 2010s turned towards the dusty G2 object on a highly eccentric orbit [12]. Further observations at $3.8 \mu\text{m}$ revealed the population of ~ 10 similar objects [13, 14] – their nature has continued to be debated. Towards the end of the decade, measurements with the near-infrared interferometer GRAVITY and the Keck telescopes detected the gravitational redshift in the spectrum of the S2 star [15, 16]. The relativistic (Schwarzschild) precession was also confirmed to a high precision [17]. Thanks to the observations with sensitive millimeter/submillimeter instruments (ALMA, SOFIA), new aspects of the dynamics and the star formation within the Central Molecular Zone were revealed. These are examples of the trend towards an increasing precision of the Galactic Center science. The GCWs were organized in 2013 in Santa Fe, USA [18], in the same year also in Granada, Spain, in 2016 in Palm Cove, Australia [19], and in 2019 in Yokohama, Japan [20].

Beyond the 2020s, the Galactic Center science has greatly accelerated thanks to the regular observations of Sgr A* by the Event Horizon Telescope. The reconstructed image of Sgr A* with the clear ring-like appearance with the diameter of $\sim 50 \mu\text{m}$ was revealed [21], later including the polarization signature [22]. The GCW in Granada in 2023 summarized these findings and generally focused on multi-wavelength and multi-scale aspects of the Galactic Center environment.

In general, there were many smaller and more specialized workshops, either organized as stand-alone meetings or as a part of larger conferences (European Astronomical Society annual meetings, American Astronomical Society meetings, IAU General Assemblies). For this reason, it is difficult to estimate the real number of GCWs that have

taken place since the identification of Sgr A and Sgr A* in the previous century. However, when we focus on the series of workshops (conferences) organized every few years with the goal to capture as complete a description of the Galactic Center as possible (multi-scale, multi-wavelength, and currently also multi-messenger approaches), the number is ~ 15 , when we include two larger conferences in 2013 (Santa Fe–Granada).

Hence, the Brno workshop (IAUS 405) is the 15th/16th edition of GCWs. It is the continuation of the tradition of previous GCWs, specifically by combining multi-wavelength and multi-messenger approaches. However, it also adds new aspects, such as new findings with the James Webb Space Telescope and the X-ray telescope XRISM. The name of the symposium, *Traversing the Galactic Center in Space and Time*, aims to stress the necessity to look at the Galactic Center on different spatial scales to understand the intricate dynamics of the region and its temporal evolution. A better understanding of accretion, star formation, and dynamical processes will be beneficial not only for the Galactic Center but for other nuclei as well. ■

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BRNO OBSERVATORY AND PLANETARIUM

By MARKO MESARČ

Located on Kraví hora in Brno, the Brno Observatory and Planetarium is one of the leading centres for science education in the Czech Republic. Founded in 1954 as a small observatory, it has developed into a modern interactive centre combining astronomy and other natural sciences. Its main goal is to present science in an engaging, clear, and entertaining way.

From Observatory to Digital Universe

The observatory was modernised in the 21st century, with a major reconstruction in 2010–2011, and in 2013, advanced new technology was introduced – a modern 3D planetarium. Its main feature is the *Digitarium*, a 17-metre dome offering immersive full-dome projections of the universe. In addition to the main dome, the facility includes a smaller planetarium, telescopes for night sky observation, an observation deck, and exhibition spaces, making it a diverse centre for science popularisation.

The Brno Observatory is not only an educational institution but also a creative production hub. Its in-house team develops original full-dome films that are shown locally and also distributed internationally. These productions combine scientific knowledge

with artistic expression, often involving collaborations with filmmakers, musicians, and designers.

One of the most important events hosted here is the *Full-dome Festival Brno*, an international festival dedicated to immersive full-dome productions with educational content. The festival brings together creators, scientists, and industry professionals from around the world, showcasing the latest developments in full-dome technology and storytelling.

Exhibition: “Universe Behind the Mirror”

The “Universe Behind the Mirror” at the Brno Observatory and Planetarium is an interactive exhibition that reveals the hidden side of the universe. It features a panoramic image of distant galaxies based on data from the James Webb Space Telescope. Visitors walk on a map of dark matter, representing the structure of the universe. The room is surrounded by mirror walls, creating an illusion of infinite space. The highlight is a cloud chamber, where visitors can see real cosmic radiation particles. The exhibition also includes models of gravitational lenses and interactive displays explaining black holes and the expansion of the universe.

Visit, Learn and Wonder

The facility goes beyond astronomy. From interactive expositions exploring dark matter, particle physics, and the microworld to a rooftop observation deck offering panoramic

views of Brno, the centre presents science in accessible and engaging ways. With up to 200 000 visitors annually (about 25 % from school excursions) and around 1 800 events each year, the centre is one of the most visited institutions of its kind in the Czech Republic. Whether you come to gaze at star clusters through a telescope, watch a breathtaking full-dome show, or explore hands-on exhibits in the exhibition, the Brno Observatory and Planetarium invites you to look up, look inwards, and imagine.

“Universe Behind the Mirror” exhibition, with the smoke chamber in the front

Birdeye view of the Observatory and Planetarium in Brno

Inside the dome of the digital planetarium (top). The observation deck (bottom).

BRNO SURVIVAL GUIDE

By PETRA SUKOVÁ

Traversing Brno in Space and Time.

Brno is easy to navigate once you accept one basic fact: Kraví hora is indeed a hill. For the conference venue, the simplest option is usually tram No. 4 to *Náměstí Míru / Masarykova čtvrť*, followed by a short walk uphill; the same tram also takes you conveniently back toward the city center. Tickets can be bought directly in trams and buses by tapping a contactless card. The standard fare is 25 CZK for 60 minutes, while a shorter 15-minute ticket costs 20 CZK if you also tap when leaving. There is also a 24-hour ticket for Brno (zones 100+101) for 90 CZK and a 5-day ticket for 250 CZK. You can search for connections here: <https://www.dpmb.cz/en>.

Route to the Welcome Cocktail: *Brno New Town Hall – Gothic cloister (B)*
Walk about 2.5 km or take tram No. 4 to *Náměstí Svobody (A)* + 5 mins walk

Route to the Conference Dinner: *Moravian Gallery – Museum of Applied Arts (C)*
Walk about 2.4 km or take tram No. 4 to *Náměstí Svobody (A)* + 6 mins walk

Shopping in Brno.

In the Czech Republic, prices are given in Czech crowns (Kč or CZK) with the current conversion rate of 1 EUR ≈ 24.4 CZK, 1 USD ≈ 21.0 CZK. Card payments are accepted almost everywhere, so in practice, you only need a small amount of cash for minor purchases off the grid. We note that it is also recommended when using the card terminal to always pay in your account's currency and let your bank do the conversion (merchants may give you worse rates if you pay in CZK with a foreign card). Also, beware of ATMs labelled "ATM": they are widely known to scam tourists with hidden fees and poor exchange rates, so we recommend using bank ATMs [see, e.g., 1, for more comprehensive guides].

Most supermarkets are open daily, typically from about 7:00 to 21:00, so buying water, fruit, or even an emergency dinner is rarely a problem – even though the conference catering is expected to be rather generous. A convenient small grocery store,

Brněnka, can be found right by the *Náměstí Míru* tram stop and is open until 20:00. For breakfast, you may wish to stop by *EGGO Bistro* or *Café Placzek*; in the afternoon, you can cool down with ice cream from *JESTĚ jednu* or enjoy coffee and cake at *Café Momenta*. One more practical detail: tap water is perfectly safe to drink.

If you wish to take home a souvenir from Brno, local design is a better choice than standard tourist magnets: the *TO JE Brno* shop offers original gifts connected with the city, from witty graphic items to objects inspired by Janáček and other local icons. Typical souvenirs from the Czech Republic include Bohemian crystal and glass, Czech garnet jewellery, and, for those who prefer something drinkable, a bottle of Becherovka or slivovice.

Night Life in Brno.

Is the scientific and social programme of the conference still not enough? Brno offers many further possibilities. For a relaxed evening, *Jakubské náměstí* is a good place to start, especially in warm weather. From there, one may continue to a traditional Czech beer hall such as *Lokál U Caiply* or *Stopkova Plzeňská Pivnice*, to one of Brno's well-known cocktail bars such as *Bar, který neexistuje*, *Malej Velkej Bar* or *Super Panda Circus*, to a music venue such as *Fléda* or *Metro Music Bar*, or even to *Cabaret des Péchés*, known for its acrobatic, burlesque, and travesti/drag-style performances. If you prefer a more classical theatrical evening, *Divadlo Husa na provázku*

is also well worth considering. You can find many more tips about enjoying Brno at <https://www.gotobrna.cz/en/>.

What to do in Brno with kids?

If you are travelling with your family, Brno offers plenty to keep children and accompanying adults happily occupied while the conference is taking place. A particularly convenient option is the *VIDA! Science Centre*, with its many interactive exhibits for children of different ages. Families may also enjoy the nearby *Open Garden*, spend an active afternoon at *BRuNO Family Park*, or try one of Brno's rope centres such as *Jungle Park* or *Rope center Proud*. *Brno Zoo* is another popular choice and, for a longer and more scenic outing, a *boat trip on the Brno Reservoir* towards *Veveří Castle* is also a lovely option.

Mini Phrasebook.

For everyday survival in Brno, the following vocabulary may be enough:

- *dobrý den* = hello
- *děkuji* = thank you
- *prosím* = please / here you go / you are welcome / almost anything
- *pivo* = beer
- *víno* = wine
- *šalina* = tram

In fact, with *prosím*, *děkuji*, and a reasonably confident nod, you can get surprisingly far. ■

[1] J. Rubeš and J. Mikulka. *Honest Guide*. <https://www.youtube.com/honestguide>. [Accessed 18-05-2026].

Route from Náměstí Svobody (A) to Welcome Cocktail (B) and Conference Dinner (C).